

Halogenation of Cadmium(II) Complexes Containing Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Cadmium(II) complexes having the formulae CdL_2X_2 , CdL_2Y_2 and $CdL'X_2$, $CdL'Y_2$, where L = pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and 3, 5-lutidine, L' = γ -picoline, X = Cl^- and Y = Br^- , when chlorinated in ethanolic medium formed anionic complexes of the type $[LH]_2[CdX_4]$, $[LH]_2[CdX_2Y_2]$ and $[L'H][CdX_4]$, $[L'H][CdY_2X]$. These compounds have been characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance and infra red spectral data.

As a part of our investigations on d^{10} metal complexes, we reported^{1,2,3} several mixed ligand and anionic cadmium complexes, where the metal ion exhibits penta-, hexa- and hepta-coordination. Halogenation reactions of several transitional metal complexes of the type ML_2X_2 , where M is a divalent metal like zinc, nickel, manganese, cobalt and copper, L is a nitrogen donor ligand and X is Cl^- or Br^- were reported⁴⁻⁸ from this laboratory earlier. It was therefore thought worthwhile to extend the halogenation reactions to the case of cadmium complexes which are hitherto uncovered. In this communication we report a number of tetrahalo cadmium(II) complexes obtained by this process.

Experimental

All the materials used were of A. R. grade. The starting materials viz., CdL_2X_2 , CdL_2Y_2 , $CdL'X_2$ and

$CdL'Y_2$, where L = pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and 3,5-lutidine, L' = γ -picoline, X = Cl^- and Y = Br^- were prepared by the method reported earlier⁹. Chlorination: Through an ethanolic suspension of dichloro and dibromo cadmium(II) complexes containing a little excess of the respective ligands, pure and dry chlorine gas was bubbled slowly till a clear solution was obtained exothermically. On cooling the solution overnight, beautiful crystalline compounds separated out which were suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and finally dried *in vacuo*. Bromination of the complexes resulted in no change of the starting material.

Purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and halogen by standard methods. Electrical conductance was measured in acetone medium ($\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution) using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CL 0102 and a dip type cell. Infra-red

TABLE I — ANALYSES, MELTING POINT AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF SOME ANIONIC CADMIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	m.p. (°C)	Cd(%)		Cl(%)		Br(%)		Λ_M (mhos)
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
$[PyH]_2[Cl_4]$	White crystalline	245 (d)	26.8	27.1	34.1	34.2	—	—	210
$[PyH]_2[CdBr_2Cl_2]$	Pale brown crystalline	210 (d)	22.1	22.3	14.1	14.1	31.6	31.7	208
$[QH]_2[CdCl_4]$	White crystalline	135	21.6	21.8	27.5	27.6	—	—	230
$[QH]_2[CdBr_2Cl_2]$	Pale yellow crystalline	155	18.5	18.6	11.6	11.7	26.4	26.5	222
$[IQH]_2[CdCl_4]$	White crystalline	150	21.4	21.8	27.2	27.6	—	—	212
$[IQH]_2[CdBr_2Cl_2]$	Pale brown crystalline	225 (d)	18.5	1.86	11.9	11.7	26.2	26.5	228
$[3,5-LutH]_2[CdCl_4]$	White crystalline	158	23.6	23.8	30.2	30.1	—	—	214
$[3,5-LutH]_2[CdBr_2Cl_2]$	White crystalline (needle shaped)	130	20.2	20.0	12.8	12.6	28.4	28.6	218
$[\gamma-picH][CdCl_2]$	White crystalline (needle shaped)	240 (d)	35.8	35.9	34.2	34.0	—	—	112
$[\gamma-picH][CdBr_2Cl_2]$	Chocolate crystalline	280 (d)	27.8	27.9	8.9	8.8	39.6	39.8	114

Py = pyridine; Q = quinoline; IQ = isoquinoline; 3,5-lut = 3,5-lutidine; γ -pic = γ -picoline; d = decompose

TABLE 2—(N-H) INFRA-RED ABSORPTIONS (CM⁻¹) OF ANIONIC CADMIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	$\delta(\text{N-H})$	$\nu(\text{N-H})$		
[PyH] ₂ [CdCl ₄]	1478 (v.s.)	3060 (m)	3180 (m)	3260 (m)
[PyH] ₂ [CdBr ₂ Cl ₂]	1483 (v.s.)	3060 (m)	3210 (s)	
[QH] ₂ [CdCl ₄]	1498 (m)	2860 (s)		
[QH] ₂ [CdBr ₂ Cl ₂]	1493 (m)	2910 (m)		
[IQH] ₂ [CdCl ₄]	1483 (v.s.)	3060 (s)	3600 (s)	
[IQH] ₂ [CdBr ₂ Cl ₂]	1488 (v.s.)	3060 (s)	3560 (s)	
[3,5-lutH] ₂ [CdCl ₄]	1463 (s)	2910 (s)	3200 (m)	
[3,5-lutH] ₂ [CdBr ₂ Cl ₂]	1458 (m)	2860 (s)	3210 (m)	
[γ -picH][CdCl ₄]	1498 (s)	3010 (m)		
[γ -picH][CdBr ₂ Cl ₂]	1493 (s)	3050 (m)	3480 (m)	

s=sharp ; v. s.=very sharp ; m=medium

spectra were recorded on hexachlorobutadiene mulls using Unicam SP 200 double beam spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical, melting point and conductance data are recorded in Table 1 and Table 2 shows the i.r. spectral data.

Results and Discussion

When chlorine gas was passed through the suspension of chloro and bromo complexes of cadmium(II) in ethanol, the following possibilities are envisaged.

1) Chlorine may get into the pyridine or quinoline ring.

2) The possibility of oxidation of the metal being ruled out here, chlorine may react with hydrogen of ethanol to form HCl which subsequently reacts with the bonded ligand base forming quaternary halides. In the present case, definitely substitution in the pyridine ring has not taken place. If it were so, the formula would have been [Cd(py.Cl)₂Cl₂] and the analysis of the compound would have indicated the presence of only two halogen atoms since ring halogen cannot be estimated by dil. HNO₃ treatment, but requires prior fusion. Further, such a compound would be a non-electrolyte.

The compounds now reported are white crystalline solids and are soluble in acetone where they behave as 2:1 or 1:1 electrolytes. Further the I. R. spectra (Table 2) indicate the presence of (N-H) stretching and bending frequencies in the region ~3000 cm⁻¹ and ~1500 cm⁻¹ respectively. Hence it is clear that anionic cadmium(II) complexes are formed involving [LH]⁺ cation formed due to solvolysis. The compounds under

report can be grouped under two categories

- Tetrahalo complexes (Tetra-coordinated) [CdX₄]⁻ or [CdX₂Y₂]⁻
- Dimeric complexes attaining tetra-coordination by dimerisation, [CdX₃]⁻ or [CdY₂X]⁻.

The first category of compounds have the composition [LH]₂[CdCl₄] or [LH]₂[CdBr₂Cl₂], as is evident from their analytical results. Their molar conductance values of >150 mhos in acetone (Table 1) are in accord with the above composition. The second category of compounds, [L'H] [CdCl₃]⁻ or [L'H] [CdBr₂Cl]⁻ are in agreement with their elemental analysis and molar conductance data. These complexes are apparently three coordinated but are presumably tetrahedral through dimerisation involving halogen bridging.

A number of four coordinated tetrahalo complexes of zinc have been reported in the literature. They were prepared directly by the reaction of zinc and pyridinium halides. In the present case the method of preparation is entirely different since the quaternary halide was obtained *in situ* from the bonded ligand base. The relevant (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies are very informative and decisive. To avoid the interference of the mulling agent—Nujol which absorbs heavily in the region of (N-H) stretching frequencies, the spectra were recorded in hexachlorobutadiene mulls which clearly distinguished the bands due to (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies as it does not absorb in this region. The $\delta(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ occurring at ~1500 cm⁻¹ and ~3000 cm⁻¹ respectively for all the compounds (see Table 2) are clearly indicative of the formation of the anionic complexes. The compounds reported now are therefore, some more examples of anionic complexes of cadmium(II) favouring tetrahedral configuration utilising 5s 5p³ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

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References

1. B. P. MISHRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 908.
2. B. P. MISHRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 238.
3. B. P. MISHRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979 (in press).
4. B. K. MOHAPATRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Inst. of Chem.*, 1970, XLII, 199.
5. M. K. MISRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Organomettal. Chem.* 1970, 22, 227.
6. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Z. anorg. allg. chem.*, 1970, 213.
7. P. C. ROY and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1146.
8. B. K. MOHAPATRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1065.
9. B. PAUL and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 532.